

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ

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**ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ
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НОМЕР-2**

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ARCHITECTURE OF DIGITAL TWINS

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ANNOTATION

In this article provides information about architecture of digital twins. Since the data collection and analysis part of Digital Twin technology is one of the most important functions in its architecture, in the article cited in the virtual window model, the virtual mirror model built-in capabilities for analyzing, evaluating, predicting and monitoring physical objects and the innovative architecture of the Digital Twins concept for communication between the real (material) and virtual world using data, the characteristics of a powerful mechanism are given.

Key words; virtual mirror models, modelling, complex configuration, visualization, industrialize, artificial intelligence.

АРХИТЕКТУРА ЦИФРОВЫХ ДВОЙНИКОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье рассказывается об архитектуре цифровых двойников. Поскольку часть сбора и анализа данных в технологии Digital Twin является одной из наиболее важных функций в ее архитектуре, в статье, цитируемой в модели виртуального окна, модели виртуального окна встроенные возможности для анализа, оценки, прогнозирования и мониторинга физических объектов и инновационная архитектура концепции Digital Twins для связи между реальным (материальным) и виртуальным миром с использованием данных приведены характеристики мощного механизма.

Ключевые слова; виртуальные зеркальные модели, моделирование, сложная конфигурация, визуализация, индустриализация, искусственный интеллект.

RAQAMLI EGIZAKLAR ARXITEKTURASI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola raqamli egizaklarning arxitekturasida haqida ma'lumot beradi. Shuni takidlash kerakki, Digital Twin texnologiyasida ma'lumotlarni yig'ish va tahlil qilish qismi uning arxitekturasidagi eng muhim xususiyatlardan biri bo'lganligi sababli keltirilgan maqolada virtual oyna modellari, virtual oyna modellari fizik ob'ektlarni tahlil qilish, baholash, bashorat qilish va kuzatish uchun o'rnatilgan imkoniyatlar va Digital Twins kontseptsiyasining innovatsion arxitekturasida ma'lumotlardan foydalangan holda real (moddiy) va virtual dunyo o'rtasidagi aloqa uchun kuchli mexanizm xususiyatlari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar; virtual oyna modellari, modellashtirish, murakkab konfiguratsiya, vizualizatsiya, sanoatlashtirish, sun'iy intellekt.

Digital Twin is a digital representation model of assets, such as a physical or virtual resource, a process or service. A DT can collect data from the sensors and their environment and it reflects its status in its own virtual domain [1]. This status could be visualized just to have a deeper insight, or it could be stored for further analysis (analytics, artificial intelligence). Furthermore, it can be also used for providing a sort of alerting system able to warn operators when something is going out of the typical controlled scenario. The functions supported by a typical Digital Twin architecture are:

- Data collection
- Data abstraction
- Data enrichment
- Modelling
- Analysis
- Visualization /Actuation

Digital Twin should include all the functionalities and should model what the particular asset can perform. An important aspect is that the virtual representation created is not a static model with fixed and unchangeable characteristics. But it represents an asset in continuous evolution where services can be continuously expanded, as the real asset changes. One of the aspects of a digital twin can be identified by the data collection. As said in the previous section it is one of the most important pillars and this activity is usually performed by a sensing layer, characterized by a multitude of sensors. These could be any real physical sensors such as UWB, which are used for precise real time location of the goods inside the warehouse or inside the manufacturing plant or RFID tags usually used for tracing the throughput of the manufacturing line, a QR/Bar code reader or virtual data source. Furthermore, there is the abstraction layer which can make transparent the origin of the data sources, providing a bridge or gateway to make all data sources indiscernible for the system itself [2]. The enrichment layer is used as the name suggest to enrich data, by creating new dimensions, aggregations of data, or elaboration of them in order to bring to light much more meaningful and useful aspects of the model considered.

The other important aspect is the modelling of the system. In order to create a virtual model, all the collected data first of all needs to be stored in a persistence layer. By having this, any further elaboration, analysis or simply visualization of the model's characteristics will be possible and furthermore it will be created a representative model that can be used in many contexts: for simulation, forecasting, optimization and so on. It's the business analytics layer that takes as input the built model and takes advantage of it by providing insights on the data simulation, provides predictions based on the received data and could be even used to try to optimize the processes analyzed [3]. Last but not least, there is the presentation layer. In order to take a look on what is happening and to interact with the model that has been built, the construction of an HMI is mandatory [4]. This can have several characteristics and can be built with many different technologies, but it has the role of a glue between the model and the physical world.

Creation Process

Figure 1. An overview of getting started with the digital twin

Developing a model of a real-world system involves multiple components and can quickly become complex [5]. A significant challenge in taking on a digital twin process can be identified in determining which is the ideal level of complexity and details in creating a digital twin model.

Models can span multiple domains and the number of statistics coming from millions of sensors and signals can become rapidly unmanageable, but at the same time a too simplistic representation of the problem could yield to false promises.

For this reason, an equilibrium between the two approaches must be found and it's not always an easy task [6]. A possible approach that tries to identify the right level of complexity is the one described in the figure-1, where are identified substantially six phases:

- Imagine
- Identify
- Pilot
- Industrialize
- Scale
- Monitor

Diving into the details, the first step is to try to identify which scenarios, processes, resource could benefit from the usage of the Digital Twin technology [7]. In order to be valuable, it should be a relevant scenario or process for the business of the company where there is still high margin of improvement.

The following step is to identify the process: in order to have a successful and trustworthy digital twin, the identification of which process to consider is essential [8]. There can be the possibility of choosing of going into deep, complex configuration of a digital twin for a specific part of a process or it can be identified in a more general and flexible configuration where a wider look to what is happening is considered. The next step is the creation of a pilot program. The pilot can be the representation of a particular use case, an entire business division and by using it in iterative and agile cycles, there is the possibility to learn more rapidly about the process itself and to maximize the return on the investment with the minimum risk [9].

Figure 2. Digital twin

Its aim is basically to try to show if further analysis or optimization can be worthy or not. Once the process has been defined and the pilot program has shown its value, the succeeding step is to industrialize the digital twin with established tools and techniques [10]. Once it is deployed, if successful, it can be taken into consideration the possibility of scaling this solution, targeting similar processes or interconnected ones. The last step in the creation process of a Digital Twin is to monitor and take measures about the implemented solution [11].

This part is very important because the construction of a DT is a continuous process where always new analysis can be performed, and new configuration can be tried out [12].

Figure 2. Digital twin

CONCLUSION

A digital twin is a reality now. It is not a concept anymore. Even though it is seen as an emerging technology, it is widely used in various industries such as manufacturing, automotive, healthcare, and smart cities.

Understanding the underlying technology stacks is critical for architecting and designing digital twin solutions. To this end, the key technology considerations are IoT, Cloud, Edge, Fog, AI, ML, Robotics, and Big Data Analytics. You can check the following articles related to these technology domains.

As a concluding remark, while architecting and designing digital twin solutions, we need to understand the business goals, requirements, and use cases based on the industry.

There may be additional industry compliance and ethical considerations that solution architects and designers need to know upfront.

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